

Nominal scanning law for PRS simulations

(Lindgren 1983 Oct 21)

For the new simulations we should work in equatorial coordinates (referred to the mean equator and equinox of J2000.0). Let $\underline{N} = [\underline{l} \ \underline{m} \ \underline{n}]$ and $\underline{K} = [\underline{l} \ \underline{j} \ \underline{k}]$ be respectively the equatorial and ecliptical triads. They are related by

$$\begin{aligned} \underline{l} &= \underline{l} \\ \underline{j} &= \underline{m} \cos \epsilon + \underline{n} \sin \epsilon \\ \underline{k} &= -\underline{m} \sin \epsilon + \underline{n} \cos \epsilon \end{aligned} \tag{1}$$

with $\epsilon = 0.4090928042$. If the sun is represented (to within a few times $10''$) by a unit vector $\underline{s}$ with ecliptical coordinates $\lambda_s, \beta_s = 0$, we have

$$\underline{s} = \underline{l} \cos \lambda_s + \underline{j} \sin \lambda_s \tag{2}$$

Let d be the time in days from JED 2447162.0 (1988 Jan 1.5 ET). The mean longitude and anomaly of the sun, and the eccentricity of the orbit at the epoch, are respectively

$$L = -1.392669 + 0.0172021240 d \tag{3a}$$

Handwritten notes: -1.3862193 (Newcomb + per.) - 1.3868088 (Bickmann) - 1.38621 = 4.89632

$$g = -0.041199 + 0.0172019696 d \tag{3b}$$

Handwritten notes: 36 (Bickmann) $\dot{g} \approx a \cdot d \dot{M} < 3 \cdot 10^{-4} \text{ rad} \approx 5 \text{ yr}$

$$e = 0.01671416 \tag{3c}$$

Handwritten notes: 5 (Newcomb) 1366 (Bickmann) $\downarrow$ $\times 2e = 9 \cdot 10^{-6} \text{ rad} = 2''$ $g = L + 1.34561$

so that, to the required accuracy ($< 1'$),

$$\lambda_s = L + 2e \sin g + \frac{5}{4} e^2 \sin 2g \tag{4}$$

The scanning law is defined with respect to the triad $[\underline{k} \ \underline{s} \ \underline{k} \wedge \underline{s}]$ by means of three angles ξ, ν, w such that the telescope triad $[\underline{x} \ \underline{y} \ \underline{z}]$ is

$$\underline{z} = \underline{k} \sin \xi \sin \nu + \underline{s} \cos \xi + \underline{k} \wedge \underline{s} \sin \xi \cos \nu \tag{5a}$$

$$\underline{x} = \langle \underline{k} \wedge \underline{z} \rangle \cos w + \underline{z} \wedge \langle \underline{k} \wedge \underline{z} \rangle \sin w \tag{5b}$$

$$\underline{y} = \underline{z} \wedge \underline{x}$$

$\langle \underline{r} \rangle$ is the normalization operator: $\langle \underline{r} \rangle = \underline{r} / |\underline{r}|$.

It remains to specify ξ , v , and w as functions of time. We assume

$$\xi = \text{constant} \quad (6a)$$

$$v = \bar{v} + a_1 \cos \bar{v} + a_2 \sin 2\bar{v} + a_3 \cos 3\bar{v} + a_4 \sin 4\bar{v} \quad (6b)$$

$$w = 2\pi R(d - d_0) \quad (6c)$$

with

$$\bar{v} = K(\lambda_s - \lambda_{s0}) \quad (7)$$

and a_i depending on (K, ξ) as in (Lindgren, 1982 June 2). The constants are

$$\xi = 43^\circ \quad (8a)$$

$$K = 6.4 \quad (8b)$$

$$R = 11.25 \quad (8c)$$

$$a_1 \dots a_4 = -0.16378, \quad -0.01308, \quad 0.00123, \quad 0.00012 \quad (8d)$$

and we may take $d_0 = 0$ and $\lambda_{s0} = 0$ to fix the initial conditions. The simulated mission spans the interval $d_1 \leq d \leq d_2$, $d_1 \simeq 100$.